

Corporate Governance Mechanisms and Earnings Quality of Listed Industrial Firms in Nigeria

Onokebhagbe Ekata Andrew¹ Lateef Olumide Mustapha² Onipe Adabenege Yahaya³

^{1,2,3}Department of Accounting and Management, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna
onosekata@hotmail.com¹ midelat2009@gmail.com² yoadabenege@nda.edu.ng³

Abstract

This study examines the effects of corporate governance mechanisms on earnings quality of 23 listed industrial firms in Nigeria. Annual reports for the period of 2006-2016 were used for the study. Regression analysis was employed as a statistical technique for analysing the data. Findings from the study reveal that board independence and chief executive officer duality have significant positive effects on earnings quality. Board gender and audit committee size have significant negative impacts on earnings quality. Board size has insignificant negative impact on earnings quality. The study recommends that the boards of listed industrial firms should be composed of more independent directors to enhance earnings quality.

Keywords: corporate governance, earnings quality, board independence, board gender, board size.

1. Introduction

Based on accounting concepts statement No. 1 of the Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB), users of financial statements utilize earnings for different purposes such as assessing management performance, evaluate future profitability, forecast future profits, and determine the risk of investing in an entity. Hence, Beaver (1998) states that standard setters are very concerned with how earnings numbers are derived as they are regarded as the most important items in financial reports to investors, analysts, boards, and senior executives (Guan, He, & Yang, 2006).

The authority of managers in using different principles for revenue recognition, matching cost with revenues and estimates and forecast is one of the factors that affect earnings quality (Marjan & Abdulrahman, 2013). While managers have access to critical information about the company and thus are expected to make decision that best reflect the actual position of the company, reasons such as earnings retention, bonus and others influence directors to act differently (Marjan & Abdul Rahman 2103). Thus, it is clear that the quality of earnings in companies is affected by the principles and discretion of managers.

Due to the separation between ownership and control, and because of asymmetric information and moral hazard problems, firm's owners always have concerns that the management who controls the owner's wealth could waste or misallocate firm assets (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Corporate Governance was then introduced to facilitate and stimulate the performance of firms by creating and maintaining the incentives to motivate insiders to maximize the firm's performance and serve as control mechanism. The corporate governance limits insiders' abuse of power over corporate resources and

provides the means to monitor behaviour of managers for accountability and giving protection to investors (Ahmed, 2006).

However, it becomes glaring that the existing corporate governance mechanisms are inefficient as they failed to protect owners' interest. Consequently, the Sarbanese-Oxley Act was introduced in 2002 in the U.S. with a view to improving corporate governance practices. Other countries, both developed and developing, followed suit. The Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) was not left out in the struggle for better corporate governance. It is noted that despite the various measures adopted by Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) to foster effective corporate governance structure and restore investors' confidence, there are still cases of manipulation or abusive accounting which is unethical by managers (Shehu, 2012).

In a bid to prevent future failure of companies, nations across the globe introduced new codes of best governance practices to align manager's interest with wealth maximization objective of shareholders; effective governance mechanism should therefore be capable of converging manager's decisions with that of the shareholders. But, despite the introduction of the codes of best governance practice in Nigeria in 2003 and its continuous modifications, the result that it has achieved can be said to be minimal.

Prior studies examine the relationship between corporate governance and financial reporting quality, earnings manipulation, financial statement fraud and weak internal controls (Beasley, 1996; Beasley, Carcello, & Hermanson, 1999; Beasley & Frigo, 2007; Carcello & Neal, 2000; Dechow, Sloan, & Sweeny, 1996; Klein, 2002; McMullen & Raghunandan, 1996; Norwani, Mohammed, & Ibrahim, 2011). Also, Cornetta, McNuttb and Tehranianc (2009), Qiao and Zhou (2007), Findlay (2006), Davidson, Goodwin-Stewart and Kent (2005), Xiea, Davidson and DaDattb (2003) use samples from US, China, New Zealand and Australia, respectively and argue that corporate governance is important in constraining the propensity of managers to engage in earnings management.

Most of these studies, however, focus more on developed economies. Andrea, Lotte and Chloe (2012) affirm that there are major differences between governance practices and disclosure standards in developed and emerging markets. Governance model in many emerging economies greatly differ from common practices in developed markets. This is an important gap in the literature that underlies this study. In addition, prior studies that investigated the impact of corporate governance on earnings quality focus on multi-industry manufacturing firms. However, this study is one of the limited studies that focus on specific sampled industry, the industrial sector.

The industrial sector refers to firms that relates to producing goods used in construction and manufacturing. This sector includes companies involved with aerospace and defence, industrial machinery, tools, lumber production, construction, waste management, manufactured housing, cement and metal fabrication. Performance in the industrial sector is largely driven by supply and demand for building construction, such as residential, commercial and industrial, as well as the demand for manufactured products.

One example of corporate governance mechanism is board independence, which refers to the presence of outside directors on the board. Board independence affects the quality of information and decisions the board takes. It is a mechanism that controls management from manipulating earnings and is expected to reduce conflict between managers and owners. Another example of corporate governance mechanism is board

gender, which monitors the activities of management of firm, having board members that differ on beliefs of what managerial behaviour is tolerable or not could improve the monitoring of managerial behaviour. It becomes evident that male and female members have differing opinions or ethical beliefs on governance that could strengthen the argument to account for gender in composing a corporate board.

Board size is another corporate governance mechanism that reduces agency conflict. Smaller boards may have the ability to make beneficial decisions and monitor the behaviour of management. On the other hand, smaller boards may not be effective in monitoring the behaviour of top management. Audit committee size as a corporate governance mechanism is the number of audit committee which engages in oversight, control, check of financial reporting process and internal control mechanisms. Board leadership structure is another mechanism that affects the management who play a role in monitoring and controlling the management of the company. The combination of the post of CEO will reduce the independence of the board.

This study examines the effects of corporate governance mechanisms on earnings quality among listed industrial firms in Nigeria. The study formulated and tested the following hypotheses:

H₁: Board independence has no significant effect on earnings quality of listed industrial firms in Nigeria.

H₂: Board gender has no significant effect on earnings quality of listed industrial firms in Nigeria.

H₃: Board size has no significant effect on earnings quality of listed industrial firms in Nigeria

H₄: Audit committee has no significant effect on earnings quality of listed industrial firms in Nigeria.

H₅: CEO Duality has no significant effect on earnings quality of listed industrial firms in Nigeria.

This study covers a period of 2006-2016. The remaining part of the work is organised into literature review, methodology, results and conclusion and recommendations.

2. Literature Review

Corporate governance as the term implies is a mechanism that is employed to reduce the agency cost that arises as a result of the conflict of interest between managers and shareholders. The role of corporate governance according to Solabomi and Uwigbe (2013) is to reduce the divergence of interest between shareholders and managers. It remains one of the most important determinants in ensuring the quality of financial reporting process. Kwakwa and Nzekwu (2003) define corporate governance as the manner in which the power of a corporation is exercised in accounting for corporate total portfolio of assets and resources with the objective of maintaining and increasing shareholders value and the satisfaction of other stakeholders while attaining the corporate mission.

In other words, corporate governance refers to the establishment of an appropriate legal, economic and institutional environment that allows companies to thrive as institutions for advancing long-term shareholders value and maximize human centred development. Smith (2012) defines corporate governance as a culture that has a common

understanding of the role of management and the board. Also, corporate governance is a mutual respect that both parties have for each other's role. It is a culture of continuous open dialogue and communication. In rounding up his views on corporate governance, Smith (2012) notes that it is about people, people doing not just what the rules say but about doing what is right. Corporate governance is a set of rules that define the relationship among shareholders, managers, creditors, the government, employees and other internal and external stakeholders in respect to their rights and responsibilities, or the system by which companies are directed and controlled.

Schipper and Vincent (2003) define earnings quality as the extent to which reported earnings faithfully represent economic earnings and argue that higher quality earnings are evidence of higher quality financial reporting. They suggest seven measures of earnings quality; persistence, predictability, variability, ratio of cash from operations to income, changes in total accruals and discretionary accruals to cash flows.

According to Yee (2006), earnings quality is defined as the ability of reported earnings to quickly and precisely reveal a firm's fundamental earnings. The more accurate and timely that reported earnings reflect shocks in the present value of expected future dividends, the higher the quality of earnings. Earnings quality is also seen in terms of absence of earnings management. This is because the intentional manipulation of earnings by managers, within the limits possible in accounting standards, may distort the usefulness of earnings to users.

Based on Agency Theory, Zahra and Pearce (1989) suggest that the presence of outside directors may affect the quality of directors' information and the decisions they take, which may lead to enhanced quality of earnings. Xie (2003) finds that where there are a large percentage of independent directors there is less likely to be earnings manipulation. However, this study uses only two control variables (size and age) and disregards other control variables such as managerial ownership, leverage, cash flow that are considered important in the model.

A study conducted by Klein (2002) uses data from 1991 to 1993 from a sample of 687 U.S. firms with control variables such as firm size, growth, performance, leverage and managerial ownership. The study documents a statistically negative association between earnings quality (measured by the Jones model) and the percentage of independent directors on the board.

Board gender refers to the total number of females on the board of directors. Many proposals for governance reforms explicitly stress the importance of gender diversity in the boardroom (Adams & Ferreira, 2009). In the UK, Higgs Report (2003), commissioned by the British Department of Trade and Industry, argues that diversity could enhance board effectiveness and specifically recommends that firms draw more activity from professional groups in which women are represented. The most extreme promotion of gender diversity occurs in Norway, where since January 2008 all listed companies must abide by a 40% gender quota for female directors or face dissolution. Subsequently, Spain enacted a law requiring companies to increase the share of female to 40% by 2015. According to Adams and Ferreira (2009), most of these legislative initiatives are based on the view that the presence of women on boards could affect the governance of companies in significant ways. We find that gender diversity in boards has significant effect on board inputs.

Women appear to behave differently than men with respect to attendance behaviour. Specifically, women are likely to have less attendance problems than men.

Board size is a pivotal element in board characteristics which may influence earnings quality. According to the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (2006), the number of board members should not be less than five and not more than fifteen members. There is however disagreement among scholars regarding the effect of board size. For example, Goodstein (1994), Jensen (1993) and Yermack (1996) claim that smaller boards (4-6) may have the ability to make beneficial decisions and monitor CEO's behaviour. The other view argues that small boards may not be effective in monitoring the behaviour of top management (Zahra & Pearce, 1989). However, the majority of prior studies argue that larger boards with varied expertise are capable of developing the synergetic monitoring of the board to mitigate the incidence of earnings management (Peasnell, 2005; Xie, 2003). A plausible explanation of this view is that smaller boards are expected to be dominated by block holders or executives while larger boards have a variety of members from different positions.

Nigeria listed companies have been required to establish an audit committee that should include at least three directors and three shareholders. The size of audit committee is employed as an indication of resources available (Habbash, 2010) which may reflect the importance of better communication and coordination. Lipton and Lorsch (2011) remark that the ability of audit committee oversight function rises when its members increases. Yermack (1996) posits that a lesser audit committee magnitude improves on firms' worth. This stand corresponds with Jensen (1993) assertion that a small sized audit committee enhances the efficiency with which the audit committee engages in oversight and control. However, Mansi and Reeb (2004) note that audit committee size that is large spends a considerable period and means to check the financial reporting process and internal control mechanisms.

In U.S., Dechow (1996) examines 96 firms subject to earnings manipulation enforcement action by the Securities and Exchange Commission and observes that firms whose CEO is also chair of the board of directors are more likely to be subjected to accounting enforcement action by SEC for alleged violation. Also, Xie (2003) examines the characteristics of the board in constraining earnings management using discretionary accruals to measure earnings management for a sample of 282 US firms for the period 1992 to 1996. He observes that earnings management is less likely to take place in firms with large boards.

Al-Abbas (2009) also examines the association between corporate governance mechanisms using board composition, board independence, separation between the responsibilities of the CEO and the Chairperson, the composition and independence of audit committees and earnings management in Saudi Arabia. His results provide no evidence that corporate governance mechanisms mitigate earnings management. Osma (2008) explores different types of earnings manipulation and analyses the effect of independent boards on constraining research and development spending manipulation in UK. They consider the entire UK non-financial firms and the sample consists of 3,438 firms for the period 1990-2002. Results from the study indicate that independent directors are capable of identifying and constraining earnings management practices.

Alves (2013) examines whether board independence improves earnings quality by reducing earnings management in Portugal using ordinary least square and two stage least square techniques to control potential simultaneity problems between board independence and earnings quality. The result suggests that strengthening the independence of boards by appointing more independent board members is a positive step towards improving earnings quality. Mohammed, Nurul and Nor (2015) examine how effective is board independence to monitoring of earnings manipulation using Beneish profit model. The study employs data from 372 publicly listed companies in Malaysia from 2010-2013. Regression analysis was used and the results show that board independence has negative and significant relationship with earnings manipulation.

Hili and Affes (2012) examine the impact of gender diversity of board of directors on earnings quality and on earnings persistence. The data were analysed using regression technique. The result did not show significant difference among firms with female and male directors. Also, Hoang (2014) examines the effect of board diversity on earnings quality. Regression technique was used to analyse the data. The study finds a significant and positive linear relationship between board diversity and earnings quality.

Similarly, Kreder (2016) examines board diversity and earnings quality nexus using a sample of S&P 1500 firms from 2007 to 2014. Data collected were analysed using regression technique. The result shows that female board presence is negatively associated with discretionary revenue recognition. Bala, Gugong and Kumai (2015) examine the relationship between audit committee characteristics and earnings quality of listed food and beverage firms in Nigeria. Data for the study were extracted from firms' annual reports and accounts. Regression test was conducted for validity of statistical inferences. The result reveals significant association between audit committee size and earnings management. Also, committee financial expertise shows inverse relationship with earnings management.

Ayemere and Elijah (2015) examine audit committee attributes and earnings quality in Nigeria. The study postulates that audit committee attributes can impact significantly, constraining accrual-based distortion of financial reporting credibility and thus improves the quality of financial reporting. Regression technique was employed to analyse the data collected. The findings show that audit committee has a constraining effect on earnings management. Yasser (2015) examines the impact of CEO duality on earnings quality in Malaysian listed companies over the period 2011-2013. Regression technique was used to analyse the data collected. The findings show that CEO duality is not associated with financial reporting quality.

Chou and Chan (2018) examine the impact of CEO characteristics on earnings manipulation from the US banking industry. Regression technique was used to analyse the data. The findings show that CEO experience and profession has a significant moderate effect on earnings management after the financial crisis of 2008. Kamarudin, Ismail and Samsuddin (2012) examine the influence of CEO duality on earnings quality using a sample of 3,019 non-financial companies listed on Bursa Malaysia from 2005-2010. Regression analysis was used to analyse the data and the result shows that earnings quality is weakened by the existence of CEO duality.

3. Methodology

The population of the study consists of twenty-six industrial firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 31 December 2016. The use of the industrial firms was appropriate for the study since they are public entities operating under strict corporate governance regulations, making their financial and accounting disclosures reliable. Census sampling technique was adopted for the study. The following model was adopted for the study:

$$DACC_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BIND_{it} + \beta_2 BGEN_{it} + \beta_3 BODSIZ_{it} + \beta_4 ACS_{it} + \beta_5 CDU_{it} + \beta_6 FS_{it} + \beta_7 Lev_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Whereas:

DACC = Discretionary accrual, defined as the difference between net income which is earnings before taxation and extraordinary item and cash flow from operating activities (Marjan, 2014)

BIND= Board Independence, measured as proportion of non-executive members in board of directors (independent directors/total directors (Chen, 2011)

BGEN = Board Gender, measured by number of female directors on the board divided by the board size (Lena, 2015)

BODSIZ = Board Size, measured by number of directors on the board (Vivienne, 2003)

ACS = Audit Committee size, measured by total number of audit committee members (Wu & Hsu, 2007)

CDU = CEO Duality, measured by CEO equals 1 if CEO is also chairman of the board and 0 if otherwise (Werner, 2009)

FS = Firm Size, measured by natural logarithm of total asset of the company (Babalola, 2013)

LEV = Leverage, measured as total liabilities divided by total assets (Sumaira & Amjad, 2013)

β_0 = Parameters

ϵ = Error term

4. Results and Discussion

Table1

Descriptive statistics

Variables	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev	Min	Max
Dacc	253	5.114632	3.29343	0.12	13.45
Bind	253	0.2389723	0.293702	0	0.75
Bgen	253	0.125336	0.2033304	0	1.3
Bodsiz	253	8.537549	2.420886	4	19
Acs	253	5.225296	1.084081	3	7
Ceodu	253	0.5573123	0.497689	0	1
Fs	253	6.756245	1.38786	1.02	10.3
Lev	253	0.5814624	0.5674727	0.01	5.28

Source: STATA 13 Outputs

The descriptive statistics for the sampled firm as shown in table 1 below indicate that the discretionary accruals for the selected firms have an approximate mean value of 5.114632; on the other hand, board independence, board gender, board size, audit committee size, ceo duality, firm size and leverage had a mean value of 0.2389723, 0.125336, 8.537549, 5.225296, 0.5573123, 6.756245, and 0.5814624 respectively. This

result implies that board independence with a mean value of about 23.8% depicts that on the average, there is a greater proportion of executive directors than the non-executive directors on the board.

Board gender shows a mean value of about 12.5% which implies that female make up 12.5% of board members in listed industrial goods firm in Nigeria and the result for board size implies that the listed industrial goods firms is made up of an average of 8 persons which is about two third of the maximum 15 members board as specified in the securities and exchange commission’s code of corporate governance of 2003. The result for the audit committee size implies that the audit committee has an aggregate average of approximately 5 for all listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Also, having an approximate mean value of about 55% for ceo duality, this basically indicate that 55% of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria have the same individuals functioning as the chairman and the CEO.

Table 2

Variance Inflation Factor

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
BIND	1.34	0.743621
BGEN	1.17	0.853252
BODSIZ	1.45	0.691633
ACS	1.17	0.855200
CEODU	1.29	0.774320
FS	1.45	0.691633
LEV	1.21	0.828585
MEAN VIF	1.29	

Source: STATA 13 Outputs.

To investigate the existence of multicollinearity the variance inflation factor (VIF) for each of the explanatory variables are computed as depicted in Table 2. The mean VIF as reported is 1.29, which is lower than (10), a number that is used as a rule of thumb as an indicator of multicollinearity problem (Field, 2000). Thus, the result supports the lack of presence of multicollinearity in the research model.

Table 3

Regression Analysis

DACC	Coefficient	Std Err	t	P>[t]	[95% Conf. Interval]	
BIND	4.071986	0.6971565	5.84	0.000	2.698802	5.445171
BGEN	-4.041698	0.9400959	-4.30	0.000	-5.893399	-2.189997
BODSIZ	-0.1244536	0.0865989	-1.44	0.152	-0.295027	.0461198
ACS	-0.6631356	0.1761236	-3.77	0.000	-1.010045	-0.316226
CEODU	1.935352	0.403176	4.80	0.000	1.141219	2.729485
FS	0.5047669	0.1529781	3.30	0.001	0.2034468	0.806087
LEV	-0.1124685	0.3418216	-0.33	0.742	-0.7857525	.5608155
No of Obs	253					
F (7, 245)	14.70					
Prob> F	0.000					
R ²	0.2958					
Adj R ²	0.2757					

Source: STATA 13 Outputs

Table 3 displays the result of the regression equation model used to test all the stated hypotheses (i.e. H₁-H₅) for this study. The result of the regression analysis can, therefore, be interpreted with a greater degree of confidence. Hence, the results for the goodness of fit test as shown in Table 3 present an adjusted R² value of about 0.2757. This in a nutshell implies that the value of the dependent variable can be explained by about 28% of the independent variables. This therefore shows that 28% changes in earnings quality of listed industrial goods firm in Nigeria could be accounted for by independent variables.

More so, the F-test statistics shows a p-value that is less than 0.05. This outcome suggests clearly that simultaneously the explanatory variables are significantly associated with the dependent variable. Empirical findings for this study show that there is a significant positive relationship between board independence and earnings quality for the sampled firms. This is evident in the p-value and t-value of 0.000 and 5.84 respectively. Hence, the study accepts the alternate hypothesis and rejects the null hypothesis. This result basically indicates that there is a direct relationship between board independence and earnings quality, this is the more independent a board is, the higher level of earnings quality. This result is consistent with the finding of Peasnell 2005, where his study opined that establishing a board that provides effective monitoring of management action depends on its independence. Thus, from an agency perspective, an independent board is more likely to be vigilant for agency problems as it includes a substantial number of non-executive directors.

Findings for the second hypothesis show that there is a significant negative relationship between board gender and earnings quality for the sampled firms. This is evident in the p-value and t-values of 0.000 and -4.30 respectively. Hence, the study rejects the null hypothesis. The result indicates that the presence of female members in the board of directors helps reduce unethical accounting practices which has a positive role in determining the quality of earnings of the sampled firms. Board size shows an insignificant negative relationship on earnings quality for the sampled firms. This is shown in the p-value and t-value of 0.152 and -1.44 respectively. The null hypothesis is therefore accepted, this implies that there is an inverse relationship between board size and earnings quality. This result is indicative of the fact that firms with large board size of directors are more effective in the control of manager's discretionary attitude. It connotes the fact that larger boards with diverse knowledge are more effective for constraining earnings management than smaller boards. This outcome contradicts the findings of Xie (2003), where it was opined that the more the numbers of members on board, the less effective the supervision to the managers.

Findings for the fourth hypothesis show that there is a significant negative relationship between audit committee size and earnings quality for the sampled firms in Nigeria. This is also evident in the p-value and t-value of 0.000 and -3.77 respectively. Therefore the null hypothesis should be rejected. This result is indicative of the fact that firms with large audit committee size are more effective in controlling earnings management. The outcome of this study is in contradiction of Chen (2009) where it was opined that large audit committee size are less efficient in controlling earnings management.

Findings for the fifth hypothesis show that there is a significant positive relationship between CEO duality and earnings quality for the sampled firms in Nigeria. This is evident in the p value and t-value of 0.000 and 4.80 respectively. Therefore the null hypothesis should be rejected. Thus as CEO duality dominance tendencies increases earnings management also decrease. That is CEO duality has a significant positive impact on earnings quality. The finding of this study is in line with the findings of Klein (2002) and Fama and Jensen (1983) were they opined that the existence of CEO duality in a firm will lead to a weaker monitoring function of the board.

Firm size shows a significant positive relationship with earnings quality for the sampled firms in Nigeria, it also shows a p-value and t-value of 0.001 and 3.30 respectively. The results indicate that large firms are less likely to engage in earnings management practices. This may possibly refer to their benefit from economic of scale compared with small firm that tend to manipulate earnings to cover their high marginal cost. On the other hand leverage shows an insignificant negative relationship with earnings quality for the sampled firms in Nigeria, it also shows a p-value and t-value of 0.742 and - 0.33 respectively.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

In each of the hypotheses, discretionary accrual was used as the criterion for earnings quality in representing the dependent variable. On the other hand, board independence, board gender, board size, audit committee size and CEO duality (proxy by BIND, BGEN, BODSIZ, ACS and CEODU) respectively were used to represent the independent variable. The result from our determination test indicates that 28% change in earnings quality of firms can be explained by corporate governance variables. The study further revealed that while a positive relationship exist between board independence, CEO duality and earnings quality; on the other hand, board gender, board size and audit committee size had a negative impact on earnings quality of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Hence, the study concludes that independent directors improves earnings quality, this means that the more independent a board is the higher the quality of earnings.

Further conclusion is that board gender reduces unethical accounting practices and audit committee enhances the quality of earnings of listed industrial goods firms. The study also concludes that the post of ceo and chairman should be maintained. The study therefore recommends that the board of directors in Nigerian industrial goods firms should be composed of more independent directors to enhance quality financial reporting.

References

- Adams, R. B., & Ferreira, D. (2009). Women in the boardroom and their impact on governance and performance. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 94, 291-309.
- Al-Abbas, M. (2009). Couality corporate governance and earnings management: An empirical study of the Saudi market. *Journal of American Academy of Business*, 15(1), 301-310.
- Alves, S. (2013). The impact of audit committee existence and external audit on earnings management: Evidence from Portugal. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 11(2),143–165.
- Ahmed, K., Hossain, M., & Adams, M. (2006). The effects of board composition and

- board size on the informativeness of annual accounting earnings. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 14(5), 418-431.
- Andrea, N., Lotte, J., & Chloe, K. (2012). Corporate governance and financial reporting quality: The case of American firms. *International Business Research*, 4(1), 71-79.
- Ayemere, I., & Elijah, A. (2015). Audit committee attributes and earnings management: evidence from Nigeria. *International J. of Business and Social Research*, 5(4) 6-10.
- Bala, H., & Gugong, B. K. (2015). Audit committee characteristics and earnings quality of listed food and beverage firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 2(2), 71-78.
- Beasley, M. S. (1996). An empirical analysis of the relation between boards of director composition and financial statement fraud. *The Accounting Review*, 71, 433- 465.
- Beasley, M. S., Carcello, J. V., & Hermanson, D. R. (1999). Just say no strategic finance. May, 52-57.
- Beasley, M. S., & Frigo, M. L. (2007). Strategic risk management: Creating and protecting value. *Strategic Finance*, 53, 24-31.
- Beaver, W. (1998). Financial reporting: An accounting revolution. Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall.
- Carcello, J. V., & Neal, T. L. (2000). Audit committee characteristics and auditor reporting. *The Accounting Review*, 75, 453-467.
- Chou, Y. Y., & Chan, M. L. (2018). The impact of CEO characteristics on earnings manipulation: Evidence from US banking industry. *Journal of Applied Finance and Banking*, 8(2), 17-44.
- Cornett, M., McNuttb, A., & Tehranian, H., (2009). Corporate governance and pay-for-performance: The impact of earnings Management. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 9, 295-314.
- David, S. (2012). Corporate governance, product market competition, and equity prices. *Journal of Finance*, 67(2), 71-78.
- Davidson, R., Goodwin-Stewart, J., & Kent, P. (2005). Internal governance structures and earnings management. *Accounting and Finance*, 45, 241-267.
- Dechow, P., Sloan, R., & Sweeney, A. (1995). Detecting earnings management. *Accounting Review*, 70, 193-225.
- Dechow, P. M., Sloan, R. G., & Sweeny, A. P. (1996). Causes and consequents of earnings manipulation: An analysis of firms subject to enforcement actions by the SEC. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 13, 1-36.
- Findlay, D. (2006). Corporate governance, corporate social responsibility and corporate performance. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 16, 641-655.
- Goodstein, J., Gautam, K., & Boeker, W. (1994). The effect of board size and diversity on strategic change. *Strategic Management Journal*, 15, 241-50.
- Guan, L., He, D., & Yang, D. (2006). Auditing, integral approach to quarterly reporting and cosmetic earnings management. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 21(6), 569-581.
- Habbash, M. (2010). The effectiveness of corporate governance and external audit on constraining earnings management practices in the UK. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 3(2), 71-79.
- Higgs, D. (2003). Review of the role and effectiveness of non-executive directors. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 9(3), 301-315.
- Hili, W., & Affes, H. (2012). Corporate boards gender diversity and earnings persistence:

- The case of French listed firms. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 12, 461-471.
- Hoang, C. T. (2014). Board diversity, earnings quality and corporate social disclosure: Evidence from Vietnamese listed firms. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 3(2), 65-76.
- Jensen, M. (1993). The modern industrial revolution, exit, and the failure of internal control systems. *The Journal of Finance*, 25(3), 831-873.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behaviour, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305-360.
- Kamarudin, K. A., Ismail, W. A. W., & Samsuddin, M. E. (2012). The influence of CEO duality on the relationship between audit committee independence and earnings quality. *Inter. Congress on Interdisciplinary Bus. & Social Science* 65(3), 919- 924.
- Klein, A. (2002). Economic determinants of audit committee effectiveness. *The Accounting Review*, 4, 435-454.
- Kreder, R., (2016). Board diversity and earnings quality: The association between female board presence and magnitude of discretionary revenue activities: Evidence from US listed firms. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Control*, 10, 25-70.
- Kwakwa, V., & Nzekwu, G. (2003). International best practices on corporate governance. *Issues in Corporate Governance*, 18-39.
- Lambert, R. (2001). Contracting theory and accounting. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 32, 73-87.
- Lipton, M., & Lorsch, J. (2011). A model proposal for improved corporate governance. *Business Lawyer*, 48(1), 59-77.
- Mansi, S., & Reeb, D. M. (2004). Board characteristics, accounting report integrity and the cost of debt. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 37(3), 71-91.
- Marjan, T. G., & Abdulrahman, R. (2013). Corporate governance and earnings quality: The experience of listed companies in Iran. *Journal of Modern Accounting and Auditing* 9(6), 790-797.
- McMullen, D. A., & Raghunandan, K. (1996). Enhancing audit committee effectiveness, *Journal of Accountancy*, 182(2), 79-81.
- Mohammed, F. B., Nurul, A. A., & Nor, B. Z. (2015). How effective is board independence to the monitoring of earnings manipulation? *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 31, 462-469.
- Norwani, N. M., Mohamad, Z. Z., & Ibrahim, T. C. (2011). Corporate governance failure and its impact on financial reporting within selected companies. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(21), 87-97.
- Osma, B. G. (2008). Board independence and real earnings management: The case of R & D expenditure. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 3, 231-260.
- Peasnell, K. V., Pope, P. F., & Young, S. (2005). Board monitoring and earnings management: Do outside directors influence abnormal accruals? *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 32, 1311-1346.
- Qiao, C., & Zhou, P. (2007). Corporate governance practices, CEO characteristics and firm performance. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 4, 197-228.
- Sarbanes, P., & Oxley, M. (2002). *Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002*. Washington, DC: U.S.
- Schipper, K., & Vincent, L. (2003). Earnings quality. *Accounting Horizon*, 67-111.
- Shehu, U. H., & Ahmed, A. (2012). Corporate governance, earnings management and

- financial performance. A case of Nigeria manufacturing firms. *American international Journal of Contemporary Research*, 2(7), 6-13.
- Solabomi, O. A., & Uwuigbe, U. (2013). Effects of corporate governance on corporate social and environmental disclosure among listed firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 2(5), 76-92.
- Xie, B., Davidson, W. N., & DaDalt, P. J. (2003). Earnings management and corporate governance: The roles of the board and the audit committee. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 9(3), 295-316.
- Yermack, D. (1996). Higher market valuation of companies with a small board of directors. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 40, 185-211.
- Yasser, Q. R. (2015). The impact of CEO duality on earnings quality in the East. *The International Journal of Business in Society*, 15(5), 706-718.
- Yee, C. (2006). Corporate governance and the quality of accounting earnings: A Canadian perspective. *International J. of Managerial Finance*, 2(4), 302-327.
- Zahra, S., & Pearce, J. (1989). Boards of directors and corporate financial performance: A review and integrative model. *Journal of Management*, 15, 291-334.